

Persuasive Conversational Agents for Environmental Sustainability: A Survey

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In the next few years, people are called upon to collectively contribute to environmental sustainability, such as mitigating climate change, reducing waste, conserving biodiversity, or promoting sustainable resource management. With this literature review, we are interested in investigating how conversational agents have been used to persuade people toward environmental sustainability behavioral change, and which design features and methods are used in the persuasion process. This field sits at the crossroads of multiple disciplines, including Computer Science, Human-Computer Interaction (HCI), Environmental Science, and Psychology, each contributing unique insights into the design and effectiveness of persuasive conversational agents. The survey proposes a structured report analyzing the current state of the art in persuasive conversational agents for environmental sustainability, considering the multidisciplinary nature of the issue. We explored multiple perspectives, including the conversational agents' design features, the persuasion strategy adopted, the environmental sustainability issue considered, and the empirical evaluation method (if an empirical study was performed). From the lessons learned, we propose a research agenda to fill the gaps in the field and a checklist to guide future research in persuasive conversational agents applied to environmental sustainability.

CCS Concepts: • **Human-centered computing** → **Natural language interfaces**; **Personal digital assistants**; *Ambient intelligence*;

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Survey, conversational agent, environmental sustainability, persuasive technology, human-computer interaction

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1 Introduction

Conversational Technologies, which enable users to interact with digital tools through natural language [108, 140], are getting more and more pervasive. They are embedded in smart physical devices (such as Alexa and Google Home) and integrated into various software applications. Conversational Technologies are currently used in many contexts of everyday life [150], such as they empower people to buy something on their preferred e-commerce website [119], listen to music [123], follow a cooking recipe [7], and take notes just using voice [97]. Conversational Agents are also widely used in phones' operating systems or applications (like Siri, the Apple virtual assistant) [70], cars [97], and customer service [66]. Additionally, the emergence of **Large Language Models (LLMs)** in AI has transformed several conversational technology applications, and also unlocked chatbots for code development, story and creative generation, and text completion and summarization [138].

Our research focuses on conversational technology used to persuade people to change behaviors, and we can refer to this category of digital tools as **Persuasive Conversational Agents (PCA)**. PCAs are effectively used to lead people to adopt healthier habits, such as committing to regular exercise [148], reducing snacking [88], or limiting alcohol consumption [100].

PCAs are also a promising interaction paradigm toward improving people's awareness and effectiveness in adopting environmentally sustainable behaviors [73]. However, their persuasive use for environmental sustainability is quite a novel research area, and a clear literature landscape on PCA is still missing.

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change argues with about 95% certainty that climate change is anthropogenic [109]. The urgent need for a green turnaround for all nations on the planet has been highlighted in many contexts, and world leaders at the **Sustainable Development Goals (SDG)** summit in September 2019 defined the 2020s as a *Decade of Action*, in which nations have to collaborate in the development of scientific knowledge and cutting-edge tools to achieve sustainability goals [48], pinpointing that everyone must implement sustainable behaviors and contribute as individuals to the "green" collective effort.

Our survey focuses on the human-centered design and evaluation of this class of systems and provides a review of the current state of the art contributing to the **Human-Computer Interaction (HCI)** field. The survey has been carried out by investigating five research questions posed to the articles involved in the analysis:

- R1 Which **High-Level Design Features** are addressed (e.g., sustainable topics covered, persuasion strategies adopted, and underlying theories)?
- R2 What **UX Design Features** are adopted in Persuasive Conversational Agents for environmental sustainability (e.g., interaction modes, agent embodiment, personalization capability, ambient awareness)?
- R3 Which is the **Participants Profile** in the **Empirical Evaluation** of Persuasive Conversational Agents for environmental sustainability?
- R4 Which is the **Study Design** in the **Empirical Evaluation** of Persuasive Conversational Agents for environmental sustainability?
- R5 What are the **Lessons Learned** on Persuasive Conversational Agents for environmental sustainability?

This article presents the literature review process and results performed to answer the above questions. We followed a systematic method to gather and extract relevant data, reducing any possible biases during information collection. We quantitatively and qualitatively analyzed and reported the results, exploring and discussing the results on the different research variables.

The major contributions presented in this work are the following:

- A systematic review of Persuasive Conversational Agents for environmental sustainability clustered into different dimensions (i.e., persuasion strategies, sustainable topics addressed, UX and conversational design features, and approaches to empirical evaluation)
- A discussion of the results and research gaps on the different variables identified from the research questions
- From the lessons learned by the studies surveyed, we derived
 - A set of actionable recommendations that identify open research gaps to be filled by future development and investigation in such category of Persuasive Conversational Agents.
 - A reporting checklist for future works on Persuasive Conversational Agents for environmental sustainability that wants to guide researchers in reporting the variables we consider particularly necessary and useful to design, develop, and report such agents.

The article is organized as follows: Section 2 presents a background overview of persuasive technology, conversational agents, and environmental sustainability, drafting the conceptual framework and research questions used to evaluate the under-review articles. Section 3 presents the systematic procedure followed. Section 4 is the core of the article, reporting the result from the analysis based on the 52 surveyed articles (from 2009 to January 2025). Section 5 delves into the discussion on the results, while Section 6 presenting a research agenda and a reporting checklist. Section 7 outlines the current limitations of this survey. Finally, Section 8 draws conclusions.

2 Research Context

Our inquiry lies at the intersection of three primary areas: Environmental Sustainability, Persuasive Technology, and Conversational Agents (see Figure 1). For each area, we have identified key aspects of interest, focusing on those that are particularly relevant both within each specific domain and across the broader field of Human-Computer Interaction. This approach also reflects themes emerging from related literature surveys [1, 2, 25, 36, 129, 151].

The conceptual framework has guided the formulation and structure of our research questions, as well as the analysis of the reviewed articles. Before delving into these aspects, we first define the main terms used in this review to prevent potential misunderstandings arising from differences in terminology across disciplines.

2.1 Background and Terminology

We define *persuasion* as modifying another subject's attitude or behavior while exchanging messages or chatting [31], inducing a person to recognize the reality of a fact [78]. In addition, the persuasion process should not deceptively impose a change in human beings but push people to reflect on improving their behaviors for a specific value (i.e., persuasion goal). In the particular case of this survey, the value of enhancing is identified in environmental sustainability.

According to Crano and Prislin [33], the persuasion goal could be achieved with spontaneous or controlled processes. The former is a process directly triggered by self-awareness by people for change and strong motivation, while the latter is a procedure that influences people's actions to achieve a final intent. In the context of persuasion with controlled processes, in 1991, Ajzen [3] proposed the **Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)**. TPB provides a conceptual framework for dealing with the complex nature of human social behavior, presenting the basis for understanding and anticipating actions performed by people in specific settings. In addition, TPB provides as its main outcome that controlled persuasive models working for people's behavioral change jointly depend on motivation (i.e., people's intention) and ability (i.e., behavioral control).

Fig. 1. Conceptual framework and related research questions.

Still, Prochaska and DiClemente [137] suggested a behavioral change model (called *Transtheoretical Model* or *Stages of Change Model*) that implies different phases in a circular process. Motivation is a continuum looping starting from *Pre-contemplation*, in which the user is unaware of the change, and motivation must be built. *Contemplation* is the phase related to the users' awareness of the change, followed by *Preparation*, where strategies for the behavioral change are set. Change occurs in the *Action* phase, in which a new lifestyle is embraced. This new behavior is sustained in the *Maintenance*, which could be interrupted by the *Relapse*, in which regression into the old behavior occurs. According to the self-blame, the user could restart the cycle or leave it completely.

Finally, Michie et al. [114] proposed a hierarchically structured taxonomy of **Behavioral Change Techniques (BCTs)**, setting a systematic and reliable specification of persuasive strategies involved in behavioral change interventions. They identified 93 possible BCTs grouped into 16 macro areas, which are Goal and planning, Feedback and monitoring, Social support, Shaping knowledge, Natural consequences, Comparison of behavior, Associations, Repetition and substitution, Comparison of outcomes, Reward and threat, Regulation, Antecedents, Identity, Scheduled consequences, Self-belief, and Covert learning.

Among the different persuasive strategies clustered by Michie et al. [114], we report a short description of the ones relevant to the current manuscript. The *shaping knowledge* strategy in environmental sustainability aims at raising awareness and enhance understanding of environmental issues by addressing knowledge gaps and – in general – educating on topics like climate change, food waste, water usage, and others. *Feedback* involves providing individuals with information about their environmental impact in a way that is accessible and actionable (e.g., providing information on user energy usage). This strategy helps make abstract information into more meaningful

metrics, motivating behavior change through real-time or periodic updates. Similarly, and usually coupled with feedback, *goal setting* encourages positive environmental behaviors by prompting individuals to commit to specific, measurable targets. This strategy relies on the psychological principle that clearly defined goals improve focus and persistence. Finally, the *social comparison* strategy leverages individuals' sensitivity to social norms by showing how their behavior aligns with that of others (e.g., the neighborhood) and motivates behavioral adjustment.

The milestones – described above – in psychological literature informed the **Persuasive Technology (PT)**, defined by Fogg [55] in 2002, as technology designed to change the attitudes or behaviors of the users through social influence and persuasion techniques provided by digital tools. In the interaction with PT, effective persuasion, as in human-human interaction [167], is usually achieved by using customized messages and specific strategies to target better the person to convince. However, thanks to advanced machine learning and data science techniques, persuasion can also be achieved using algorithms that automatically fit messages according to the final user's motivation and capabilities [23, 37, 88].

In the health field [92], several persuasive digital systems are particularly relevant in the literature. For example, there are systems influencing positive eating behaviors by avoiding snacking [88], smoking cessation [9], and physical activities [6]. Another intensely explored area is educational persuasive technology to improve motivation in reading and writing in children [103] or to encourage students to achieve milestones and study deadlines in a course [67].

Environmental sustainability is the practice of utilizing natural resources in a way that protects the environment for future generations [96]. This includes preserving biodiversity, lowering pollution, and using less energy and water. Individuals and organizations can limit their environmental effects to achieve environmental sustainability [46]. Examples are substituting fossil fuels with renewable energy sources (e.g., solar and wind power), reducing waste and water usage, using electric or public transportation, and supporting energy conservation programs.

In 2015, United Nations Member States signed the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development [42]: a unifying framework for peace and prosperity for people and the planet, both for now and the future, clustering world issues into 17 goals. Among these goals, topics such as combating climate change and fighting to protect oceans and forests represent some of the environmental sustainability issues that must be addressed in the next decade.

Different strategies to induce more environmentally sustainable behaviors have been explored in recent years. For example, several studies [32, 74, 173] showed that the real-time visualization of domestic energy consumption leads to more responsible consumption, especially over long-term exposure [84]. Other works [8, 117, 173], instead, investigated the ability of persuasion techniques in HCI, such as self-monitoring, advice, rewards, and gamification, to lead to more sustainable behaviors. In addition, according to [47, 152], in the Human-Computer Interaction field, there is a growing interest in sustainability; several challenges must be addressed, and numerous issues must be well-considered and tackled [18, 94].

Conversational Agents (CA) are a promising persuasive technology for environmental sustainability [61, 144]. We define *Conversational Agents* as the set of technologies that interact with users through natural language [108, 140]. In the current literature, terms such as CA, conversational technologies, chatbots, agents, and dialog systems are often used as synonyms [56]. Conversational agents can be classified according to different criteria. Sometimes, they are categorized according to the channel they use to interact with people: voice (speech-based CA) or textual messages (text-based CA).

Another taxonomic method involves distinguishing between different implementation approaches [80]. Conversational technologies have evolved from rule-based systems – exemplified by one of the first conversational agents, ELIZA [168] – to data-driven approaches that leverage

traditional machine learning models and, more recently, transformer-based architectures and LLMs [164]. The advent of transformer-based agents has empowered the conversational interaction capabilities of CAs – overcoming the lack of flexibility and scalability of traditional rule-based systems [158] and enabling more sophisticated features such as translation, summarization, problem-solving, or creativity [138]. However, the usage of LLM-based conversational agents raises unpredictable practical and ethical concerns, including bias, misinformation, hallucinations, and privacy issues [172].

Finally, an additional classification attribute for CAs is their *embodiment*, i.e., the form in which conversational agents are presented. Embodiment ranges from physically actuated robots [41] to purely digital virtual assistants [57], as well as IoT devices (e.g., Alexa, Google Home) that can be integrated into home automation ecosystems [112, 150].

CA has been proven to influence human behavior in various ways, including increasing adherence to medical treatment, as reviewed by Gentner et al. [58] and influencing consumer behavior [83]. For instance, van Baal et al. [163] explored an AI chatbot’s ability to deliver COVID-19 protective behavioral interventions, demonstrating an increased likelihood of participants getting tested for COVID-19 symptoms. Similar results were previously found by Miner et al. [118], which tested a chatbot encouraging the adoption of public health guidelines. Still, Tsai et al. [160] investigated how chatbots and their persuasive communication strategies impact consumer engagement and brand awareness while navigating an online website of a company.

2.2 Research Questions

The different themes emerging from the Conceptual Framework depicted in Figure 1 provide the classification dimensions and sub-dimensions to organize our space of analysis into four main research questions and to structure a final orthogonal research question focused on “lessons learned”.

R1 Which **High-Level Design Features** are addressed (e.g., sustainable topics covered, persuasion strategies adopted, and underlying theories)?

This research question examines three key pillar design dimensions of our survey. First, it investigates the *sustainability topics* addressed, using SDGs as a framework to understand environmental priorities and critically assess the sustainable topics covered by the works, as SDGs are currently the global standard for tracking sustainable development progress [43]. Second, it explores the *persuasive theories* that informed PCA development, recognizing that the application of behavioral theories enhances conceptual rigor and enables hypothesis-driven evaluation of PCAs. Third, it analyzes the specific *persuasion strategies* adopted, since their selection plays a critical role in how users process persuasive messages [28], with different strategies being systematically categorized using hierarchically structured taxonomies like the one proposed by Michie et al. [114] to map the different strategies adopted by the analyzed articles.

R2 What **UX Design Features** are adopted in Persuasive Conversational Agents for environmental sustainability (e.g., interaction modes, agent embodiment, personalization capability, ambient awareness)?

This research question examines the user experience design characteristics of PCAs across multiple dimensions. It investigates the *input and output interaction modes* (speech or text), recognizing that the communication channel influences cognitive load, accessibility, and affective response [104]. The question also explores *initiation methods*, distinguishing between passive agents that wait for wake-up actions and proactive agents that anticipate user needs, noting that while proactive systems can increase engagement, they may risk perceived

intrusiveness or reduce user agency [13]. It analyzes agent *embodiment*, as the representation of conversational agents—whether visual, physical, or virtual—affects anthropomorphism and can foster engagement or provoke uncanny perception [38], with different *shapes* carrying symbolic meanings that affect user reactions. The question addresses *gender* representation, since digital agents often reproduce social stereotypes and influence user preference and trust [49, 125], making it important to critically assess these design decisions. It examines *response generation methods*, comparing rule-based systems that offer predictability with generative models that provide flexibility and naturalism [80, 113]. The question investigates *personalization features* extracted from users (such as sentiment analysis or emotion recognition), as adaptive agents incorporating user emotion or personality data can significantly enhance persuasion [89]. Finally, it explores *ambient awareness capabilities*, examining whether PCAs can perceive external environmental phenomena relevant to sustainability, such as energy consumption and user interactions with home appliances, leveraging the growing integration of conversational agents with IoT and energy data systems [91, 150].

R3 Which is the **Participants Profile** in the **Empirical Evaluation** of Persuasive Conversational Agents for environmental sustainability?

This research question examines the demographic characteristics of participants in empirical evaluations of PCAs for environmental sustainability. It considers *sample size* as a critical factor, since it directly impacts statistical validity and inferential strength, influencing the generalization of results [21, 98]. The question also investigates participants' *age distribution*, recognizing that age-related differences in technology adoption, cognitive style, and ecological concern are documented in the scientific literature [26, 130]. It analyzes *gender* composition, as it may affect receptivity to persuasive cues of the technology [130]. Additionally, it examines *participants' educational level*, acknowledging that education influences sustainability literacy and critical thinking, potentially moderating the cognitive processing of persuasive messages [86].

R4 Which is the **Study Design** in the **Empirical Evaluation** of Persuasive Conversational Agents for environmental sustainability?

This research question examines the methodological characteristics of empirical evaluations of PCAs for environmental sustainability. It investigates the *nature of the prototype* in PCA behavior, distinguishing between fully autonomous, partially autonomous, and fully human-controlled systems, as clarifying the level of automation ensures transparency regarding system capabilities and experimental validity [12, 98]. The question analyzes the research *design methods* employed, recognizing that experiments allow researchers to determine causal relationships that can yield significant scientific insights [21, 98]. It examines *study duration* as a critical factor that influences various aspects of user experience and usability [159]. Additionally, it explores the *data collection* techniques utilized, acknowledging that within HCI, different methodologies exist to collect data (such as self-reports and interaction logs) which provide a richer understanding of participant engagement [21, 98].

R5 What are the **Lessons Learned** on Persuasive Conversational Agents for environmental sustainability?

Synthesizing lessons learned on PCA for environmental sustainability with a more qualitative approach helps to consolidate and ground the field's progress in order to identify underexplored avenues for future works. Such analysis could be performed on the three main dimensions of the current survey (i.e., PCA design, persuasion, and technological approach).

3 Method

We performed a complete analysis of the scientific literature to address the research questions of how conversational agents are used in persuading people for environmental sustainability behavioral change and which design features and methods are used in the persuasion process.

Inspired by the work of [25, 151] and the guidelines by Nightingale [128] to perform a systematic literature review, we conducted this survey following the PRISMA workflow [132]. In the following sections, eligibility criteria, selection process, and query performed are detailed.

3.1 PRISMA Method

Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) [132] is a well-known approach in the literature for systematic reviews and meta-analyses. In fact, it allows researchers to demonstrate the review's quality, enabling experimental replications and organizing the manuscript with headings and contents in a structured way that is easy for the reader to find. In addition, readers are enabled to evaluate the study's advantages and disadvantages easily [132].

As depicted in Figure 2, the PRISMA method consists of five steps. The first phase is the identification, where the articles are gathered from different sources. In the next phase, the *screening*, duplicates are removed, and articles are filtered according to their eligibility based on titles and abstracts. The *eligibility* phase analyzed the previously extracted articles, looking at their entire full text and the eligibility criteria. Finally, in the *inclusion* phase, all the articles selected are deeply analyzed, reporting their results in Section 4.

3.2 Eligibility

Following the guidelines pointed out by Kitchenham et al. [93] and the research questions, we surveyed the articles to include the ones reporting on work that intersects conversational agents interaction, persuasive technology, and environmental sustainability. Thus, articles were included in the present survey according to the following eligibility criteria:

- They addressed the query based on title, abstract, and keywords described in the Section 3.3;
- they explicitly declared to apply persuasion with one or multiple persuasion strategies;
- they addressed environmental sustainability goals;
- the interaction occurs with a conversational agent;

Articles were excluded in the case:

- They were published before 2002;
- they were published after the day of the query running (i.e., after February 1st, 2025);
- they are inaccessible to the authors;
- they do not report quantifiable details on the conversational agent features, persuasion, and sustainability topic to assess the research question.

3.3 Query

The method used to collect the set of articles included in the initial dataset of the survey grounds on the terms used in their title, abstract, and keywords. The collection of keywords used in the search aims at targeting conversational agents, persuasion, and environmental sustainability. In order to address the technological component of the survey, we selected terms such as *conversational technology*, *dialog system*, *chatbot*, *conversational agent*, *embodied conversational agent*, *virtual agent*, *social robot*, *intelligent personal assistant*, and *large language models*. Inspired by the taxonomy provided by Michie et al. [114], to target the possible persuasion strategies, we used terms such as *goal setting*, *planning*, *feedback*, *monitor*, *social support*, *shaping knowledge*, *natural consequences*, *comparison of behavior*, *associations*, *repetition*, *substitution*, *comparison of outcomes*,

reward, threat, regulation, identity, self-belief, covert learning, social comparison, and awareness; in contrast, *persuasion, behavioral change, and nudge* as broad terms. Finally, the terms observed as familiar in literature for the topic issue have been identified as *environmental sustainability, sustainable development, food management, water management, sustainable mobility, eco-system, food sustainability, water sustainability, energy consumption, and energy management*.

We carried out the search on Scopus, IEEE Explore, ACM Library, and Web of Science since they are relevant databases in the Computer Science field. Scopus and Web of Science are among the largest datasets containing research items from different fields and venues, while ACM and IEEE organizations have published relevant works in the human-computer interaction field. The different queries have been adjusted to fit the search engine syntax, and the terms listed above have been adjusted to include alternatives and pluralizations. For example, we report the query run on Scopus:

```
TITLE-ABS-KEY (
  ("conversational technolog*" OR "dialog* system*" OR "chatbot*" OR
  "conversational agent*" OR "embodied conversational agent*" OR "virtual agent*" OR
  "social* robot*" OR "intelligent personal assistant*" OR "LLM*" OR
  "large language model*" OR "generative AI")
AND
  ("persuasi*" OR "behavior* chang*" OR "nudg*" OR "goal* setting*" OR
  "planning" OR "feedback*" OR "monitor*" OR "social support" OR
  "shaping knowledge" OR "natural consequence*" OR "comparison of behavior" OR
  "associations" OR "repetition*" OR "substitution*" OR "comparison of outcomes" OR
  "reward*" OR "threat*" OR "regulation*" OR "identit*" OR "self-belief" OR
  "covert learning" OR "social compar*" OR "awar*")
AND
  ("environment* sustainab*" OR "green*" OR "ecologic*" OR "eco" OR "climat*" OR
  "sustainable development" OR "food manag*" OR "water manag*" OR
  "sustainab* mobility" OR "eco-system*" OR "food sustainab*" OR "water sustainab*" OR
  "energy consumpt*" OR "energy manag*")
)
```

We exported the query results in **comma-separated value (CSV)** files and merged them into a spreadsheet. We manually included a set of possible topic-related articles that were not in the outcome of the query results but considered relevant based on the authors' prior domain expertise and literature scraping. After this set expansion, we removed duplicated documents.

3.4 Selection

After the initial screening (that removed articles not written in English, published before 2002, and not classified as scientific articles), the remaining 544 articles were analyzed twice on the eligibility criteria (previously defined in Section 3.2), from two different perspectives. The former was high-level access to the criteria based on the title, abstract, and keywords of the works, which led to the exclusion of 356 articles. The latter was an in-depth analysis performed by reading the full text of works considered eligible in the former analysis and performing the backward and forward reference chaining investigation; in this phase, 37 more articles were excluded, leaving 52 studies included in the systematic literature review.

Based on the aforementioned process, in both phases, two independent reviewers performed the analysis. To determine if the two reviewers performed consistently, the inter-rater reliability was computed using Cohen's Kappa statistic [29, 111] on the entire set of articles, resulting in a final value of 0.94. In cases of disagreement between the two reviewers, a third reviewer was consulted to make the final decision about the inclusion or exclusion of the article.

Table 1. Research Questions Associated with Variables' Name, Type, and Approach used for the Extrapolation of the Data

Research Questions	Variables	Type	Approach
R1	Sustainability Topic	Categorical	Top-down
	Persuasion Theory	Qualitative	Pattern-based
	Persuasion Strategy	Categorical	Top-down
R2	Agent's Input/Output modalities	Categorical	Bottom-up
	Agent's initiative	Categorical	Top-down
	Agent's embodiment	Categorical	Top-down
	Agent's shape	Categorical	Bottom-up
	Agent's gender	Categorical	Top-down
	Agent's response generation	Categorical	Top-down
	Extraction of user features	Categorical	Bottom-up
Agent's integration with the external environment	Categorical	Bottom-up	
R3	Participants' number	Numeric	Analytic
	Participants' age	Numeric	Analytic
	Participants' gender	Categorical	Top-down
	Participants' educational level	Categorical	Bottom-up
R4	Nature of the prototype	Categorical	Top-down
	Empirical Validation Methodology	Categorical	Bottom-up
	Study duration	Numeric	Analytic
	Method of data collection	Categorical	Bottom-up
R5	Lesson learned on PCA for environmental sustainability	Qualitative	Pattern-based

3.5 Data Extraction and Analysis

Starting from the research questions (see Section 1) and the conceptual framework (see Figure 1 in Section 2), we codified 23 variables. The variables have three types [25]: *numerical* (e.g., participants' number), *categorical* (e.g., persuasion strategy), and *qualitative* (e.g., lesson learned on the UX design). Table 1 shows and summarizes all the variables.

Numerical variables were extracted by directly looking at the information reported in the article. *Categorical* variables were extracted following two approaches: *top-down* or *bottom-up*. In the former, the variables' values are based on taxonomy from the previous scientific literature. For example, in the case of the research question R3, persuasion strategies are based on the taxonomy proposed by Michie et al. [114]. In the latter (i.e., bottom-up approach), the values of the variable are generated by clustering the relevant information extracted from the articles reviewed.

4 Results

This section reports the results of the 23 research variables mapped into the five research questions.

The PRISMA process (described in Section 3 and represented in Figure 2) allowed us to obtain a set of 52 articles that are discussed in this literature review. The full list and references of the surveyed manuscripts are reported in Appendix A.

Finally, Figure 3 reports the analysis of the publication trend of persuasive conversational agents for environmental sustainability over the years. The dotted line, representing the trend (polynomial trend of degree 2), is positive, indicating a growing interest in this research field over time. This trend is linked to the growing interest in conversational agents, thanks to the rising popularity of LLMs [172].

Fig. 2. PRISMA format diagram of the presented systematic review.

Fig. 3. Number of articles over the last years.

Fig. 4. Sustainable topic (R1.1) distribution.

Fig. 5. Persuasion strategy (R1.3) distribution.

4.1 R1: High-level Design Features

First of all, to analyze the different shapes of sustainability addressed by the works, we mapped the Persuasive Conversational Agent’s purpose into the SDGs. According to Hansson et al. [73], SDGs cannot be considered mutually independent since the complexity of dealing with a topic implies touching others. However, we decided to perform a one-to-one map of PCAs’ purposes into SDGs to have clusters of articles and better identify possible patterns in this research topic. The mapping has been conducted considering the aim of the agent and its described features in the articles with the most suitable SDG that represents it (Figure 4). The results show that *Responsible Consumption and Production (SDG 12)* has been the primary target with 20 agents (39%). 12 articles (corresponding to the 24%) were considered to persuade on *Affordable and Clean Energy (SDG 7)*, while eight focused on *Climate Action (SDG 13)*. Five articles addressed *Sustainable Cities and Communities (SDG 11)*. The rest of the articles focused on *Decent work and economic growth (SDG 8)*, *Quality education (SDG 4)*, and *Life on Land (SDG 15)*.

Secondly, we analyzed the topic of persuasion through two main lenses: to understand which persuasive strategies the agent adopted and to persuasive theory - if any. We mapped the conversational agents’ strategies using the taxonomy proposed by Michie et al. [114], previously described in Section 2. The results (Figure 5) show that 41% of agents use *Feedback and Monitoring* as their

Fig. 6. Nature of the prototype (R4.1) distribution.

Fig. 7. Agent's gender (R2.5) distribution.

main persuasion strategy. The next most common persuasion technique is *Shaping Knowledge*, used by nine articles (18%). Eight articles used a mix of multiple persuasion techniques at the same time (usually a mixture of *Feedback and Monitoring*, *Behavior Comparison*, and *Goals and Planning*), while three articles focused on *Social Support* and three others on *Gamification*. Only two articles used the *Reward and Threat* technique. Finally, the remaining articles used only once *Dialogue Style*, *Natural Consequences*, *Repetition and Substitution*, *Self-Belief*, and *Identity*. Regarding the analysis of implemented persuasive theories, only 18 articles are based on specific theories. In addition, such theories are mixed. Particularly relevant is the presence of the *Interactive forms of feedback theory* by McCalley and Midden [110] in four studies. McCalley and Midden [110] theory grounds on encouraging energy-saving behavior by providing consumers with rapid energy feedback.

To sum up, the **High-Level Design Features** analysis of conversational agents used to persuade people for more environmental sustainability behaviors pointed out that **Responsible Consumption and Production (SDG 12)** is the most common SDG addressed and **Feedback and Monitoring** is the most used persuasive strategy delivered by the agents.

4.2 R2: UX Design Features

When analyzing the UX design of a conversational agent, first of all, the input and output modalities must be considered. 18 articles used a speech-based input system, while the others 33 used a text-based approach. More mixed is the approach used for the output modalities of the different agents under survey. Several articles relied on a text interface (e.g., message app or desktop application), while 12 articles involved a speech interface (including voice synthesizers). Several articles present displays, and five also use lights as support in the output. Finally, eight articles also use other output systems (e.g., facial expression – in the case of virtual agents, texts or images on the screen).

Two main strategies must be considered when Conversational Agents initiate the interaction with users [34, 44]. The conversational technology could be passive and wait for a user call (using a hotspot/wake-up word), or it could be proactive and initiate the conversation triggered by some events (e.g., a notification about the overconsumption of energy by a household appliance). 24 articles presented a proactive agent, while 16 used a passive agent. 11 works used a mixed-initiative strategy as presented in Figure 8.

The embodiment and shape of conversational agents are varied (Figure 9). Research results show that 30 chatbots were embodied textually, 12 in message applications (e.g., telegram, slack), 13 in a desktop application, and five implemented in mobile applications. Still, 10 works presented agents were embodied in robots, while seven virtual agents (i.e., a digital artifact with certain physical characteristics usually shown on screen) have been distributed. We found in one case that the conversational agent has been embodied into an existing IoT device (i.e., a smart thermostat de Vos

Fig. 8. Agent's initiative (R2.2) distribution.

Fig. 9. Agent's embodiment (R2.3) distribution.

et al. [40]), while in another case, it has been designed and built as a new device for a speech-based conversation.

27 of the works reported information about the gender of the conversational agent (see Figure 7), with the majority (i.e., 14 articles) reporting conversational agents with neutral sex. 10 articles presented agents with the female sex, while just one is male. Two works have been categorized as special. In fact, in the work of Nakajima and Lehdonvirta [124], on a conversational agent equipped with a screen, there are avatars representing family members. At the same time, in the work of Khashe et al. [90], both male and female conversational agents have been employed as a factor in the study design (empirical experimentation), finding that participants are more likely to follow instructions by female communicators.

According to Cahn [20] and Hussain et al. [80], response generation could be implemented mainly by defining rules or using AI-driven generative models. In recent years, thanks to the recent advances in the AI field with the introduction of the transformers models [164], we can further distinguish the generative models between traditional knowledge-based CA and new large language model ones (i.e., LLM-based). From the review performed, we found 22 conversational agents created with a rule-based method, 19 articles used LLM-based conversational agents, and the remaining six used knowledge-based ones.

Conversational technologies could also be enriched with additional digital features that detect and store users' parameters and use those data to personalize the dialogue. Only nine CA in the review have added some components to extract users' features. In the case of [10, 69, 170] used emotion and sentiment recognition models to detect such user's features during the interaction with the agent, while Yamawaki et al. [171] used a dynamic emotion expression tool on top of their persuasive virtual agents to show happiness or sadness according to the message just delivered to the user. Gunawardane et al. [69] and Bruzzone et al. [17] employed sentiment analysis to find the best positive recipe to suggest to users. In addition, Castellano et al. [24] used a system of Convolutional Neural Networks for rubbish recognition. The system can recognize the item to be thrown away and suggest the bin in which to throw it. Finally, [116] simulated a camera to perceive users' stimulus to detect social clues of the users, while Mahmud et al. [105] to identify and greet the user.

Today, conversational technologies are widely deployed and used by people [150]. Moreover, these technologies are often integrated with external services of the environment in which they operate, especially in home automation environments (e.g., setting the morning routine to raise the shutters and turning on lights) [39]. 36 of the articles reviewed in this survey present features labeled as *external environments*, meaning that the article shows an integration of the CA with one or multiple devices in the home-automation environments or with some external services (e.g., urban-mobility API [45]). In particular, in 23 cases, the CA uses IoT sensors in the home

automation context to enrich the conversation. In addition, in the case of Ramasubbu et al. [139], the sensors are in an office automation context (i.e., IoT sensors are placed in an office, similar to having them in home automation), and for Suanpang and Pothipassa [154] the agent is integrated with IoT data from tourism infrastructure. In two cases [45, 95], conversational technology has been integrated with API related to public transportation and urban mobility. Similarly, Kanayo et al. [87] integrated API to access energy-related news and energy datasets. In four cases, the agents have been integrated with API or custom services to recognize and analyze food. In particular, Gunawardane et al. [69] used an external API based on TensorFlow object detection for food recognition to generate recipes, avoiding food waste; Petruzzelli et al. [135] used external datasets to retrieve recipe data, sustainability scores, and macro-nutrient; Sun and Hsiao [156] created an agent integrated within a platform containing information on waste items and their categories; Mahmud et al. [105] proposed an integration with a recognition system to classify waste materials and actuation to open the correct compartment of the trash bin for waste disposal. Three articles (i.e., [17, 106, 127]) used **Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG)** to enhance the capabilities of conversational agents in generating contextually relevant responses from external datasets or knowledge sources. Finally, Jasmy et al. [82] presented a conversational agent integrated with Amazon API to recommend sustainable related products.

To sum up, the **UX Design Features** investigation pointed out that there is no specific direction on conversational agents' input and output methods to persuade people to have more sustainable behaviors, while **rule-based** technique is the most common deliver response generation with an increase of **LLM-based** agents during the time. Still, results pointed out that **proactivity** is the most common initiative method and **chatbot** (i.e., the textual interface on an application) is the most common embodiment adopted, with **neutral** sex. Finally, such conversational agents are not intensely personalized with the extraction of user features, while they employ **external environment** integration in the conversations.

4.3 R3: Participants Profile

Not all articles contain an empirical study. 41 of the 52 selected articles have one, while the remaining present PCAs with a focus on design and implementation perspectives. A total of 3,938 people participated in the selected studies, with an average of 101 ($M=100.97$, $SD=141.72$). 27 of the studies report information about the age of participants. Subjects' age mean is 27.12 ($SD=8.5$), while a weighted average (using the number of people involved in the study as a weight factor) produces a result of 27.54. Only 23 of the articles report data about the gender distribution of people involved in the experiments. A total of 1,443 women ($M=62.74$, $SD=85.20$) and 2,007 men ($M=87.26$, $SD=85.20$) have been involved. 28 of the 41 studies report the subjects' educational level; most people involved are university students (undergraduate or graduate), while three experiments were conducted with primary school children, and two involving energy experts.

4.4 R4: Study Design

34 articles (of the 41 having a study) present information on the nature of the prototype. As Figure 6 shows, 29 studies involved conversational agents coded using different tools, for example, using DialogFlow¹ [45] or other low-code instruments as well as recent OpenAI API.² Five articles, instead, present a study with conversational agents recreated with the **Wizard of Oz (WoZ)** technique. The WoZ technique is a user-experience research method where participants interact with a digital system that they believe to be fully implemented, but which is actually operated by a human behind

¹cloud.google.com/dialogflow

²openai.com/api/

Fig. 10. Empirical Validation Methodology (R4.2) Fig. 11. Methods of data collection (R4.4) distribution.

the scenes. This method is used to test and refine prototypes, particularly those involving AI and complex interactions like Conversational Agents, allowing researchers to gather feedback on design and usability before developing the actual technology.

To assess the methodologies used in the design of the studies, we framed what was reported in articles into well-known methods in the literature [21, 98]: comparative evaluations (i.e., between or within designs), case reports, and focus groups, graphically reporting results in Figure 10. 17 articles (that included a study) performed a randomized data collection, using a between or within design with fixed factors. Of the remaining articles, 22 studies reported data about a specific case study. In these cases, the sample size of users who tried the conversational agent is small and usually involves experts from a specific sector. Finally, in two cases, a focus group was performed.

As regards the data collection methods, grouping was performed, referring to the structures used in the works: interaction and questionnaires, quantitative, and observations. The results are reported in Figure 11. 27 studies were conducted with a data collection method summarizable in interaction and questionnaire: during the experimentation session, first, users interacted with the agent, and then a post-questionnaire to evaluate attitude (persuasion effectiveness) and user experience. Four articles, instead, collected quantitative data about users' energy consumption. Three articles used qualitative approaches to analyze user interaction with the agents. In addition, four more articles used mixed approaches integrating qualitative insights with quantitative data from energy consumption and logged data generated from user interaction with the application. Finally, two articles organized data collection by taking notes during the observation of the experience.

Most of the works used self-developed questionnaires (reporting the items in the material of the study). Sometimes such custom questionnaires were supported or completely based on well-known literature works, such as the **Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT)** [165], **Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)** Questionnaire [4], **Parasocial Interaction (PSI)** [77], **System Usability Scale (SUS)** [16], perceived humanness [76], and perceived persuasiveness [99].

22 studies report the time duration of the experimentation. 14 works (64%) are short-term, and the experiments last from 30 to 95 minutes. The remaining three articles have longer-term studies conducted in more ecological settings (i.e., testing of their digital tools in the field and not in a laboratory setting). Six studies [5, 54, 75, 82, 106, 124] have a duration in the order of weeks or a month, Suanpang and Pothipassa [154] with a duration of six months, while Bourgeois et al. [14] performed an extended study with a duration of eight months.

To sum up, the analysis of the **Study Design** of the surveyed articles pointed out that conversational agents persuading people to have more sustainable behaviors were mainly tested using single sessions and interaction with the agents to contribute with a **case report**. The data collection method preferred is **questionnaires** after interaction with the agent, and sessions usually **last**

from 30 to 95 minutes. Finally, researchers preferred to make users interact with a **working prototype** rather than using a Wizard of Oz technique.

4.5 R5: Lessons Learned

In this section, the results extracted by analyzing the R5 research variable with a more qualitative approach that directly maps into the variables are reported. The study's findings are reported in the subsequent sub-sections, which are divided according to the conceptual framework outlined in Section 2.2. Thus, the sub-sections are *Environmental Sustainability*, *Persuasion*, and *Conversation and Technology*.

4.5.1 Environmental Sustainability. Aligned with the descriptive findings discussed in Section 4.1, a recurring sustainable topic addressed is energy conservation. Multiple studies have found that persuasive feedback, particularly when social or evaluative in nature, results in more significant energy savings than factual feedback alone. Negative social feedback from robotic agents can significantly reduce household electricity usage during appliance operation, emphasizing the importance of affective and socially contextualized cues [71, 72, 115, 166]. Similarly, PCAs that provide personalized, real-time feedback have demonstrated potential in household energy management by increasing awareness and encouraging more efficient use of appliances [27, 40, 75, 90]. More specifically, with energy saving directly linked to the building environment, PCAs are recognized to induce energy savings by promoting practices such as turning off unused devices or moderating heating [87, 139, 170]. However, according to de Vos et al. [40], automating actions (e.g., via smart thermostats) without addressing users' intrinsic motivations or environmental awareness is insufficient for lasting behavioral change.

In the domain of mobility, PCAs have also shown potential to shift user preferences toward environmentally friendly transport. Notably, chatbots that promote shared mobility options such as public transit or e-bikes can positively shape normative beliefs and intentions, contributing to sustainable urban transport systems [45, 95, 107], highlighting the PCAs' capability to bridge the gap between infrastructural offerings and user behavior, particularly in the recent context of smart cities.

Examining food sustainability, chatbots and recommendation engines informed by sustainability metrics, such as carbon or water footprint, have been used to guide consumers toward lower-impact dietary choices [69, 135, 174]. Encouraging plant-based diets or decreasing food waste is viewed not only as a resource conservation issue but also as a behavioral challenge that may be addressed persuasively through digital interventions.

In waste management and recycling, educational agents and gamified systems have effectively promoted sustainable behaviors, particularly among children and younger demographics. Social robots and chatbots used in serious games or classroom settings have led to increased recycling knowledge and positive behavioral intentions [24, 54, 105].

A broader implication across studies is that emotional engagement, personalization, and social contextualization significantly enhance the impact of sustainability-oriented PCAs. Systems that integrate care-based design [11], community values [10], or shared cultural narratives [127] tend to promote more durable and meaningful behavior change.

However, studies warn that short-term interactions lack real-world context and can undermine the long-term effectiveness of PCAs in promoting sustainability [60, 61]. Also, challenges of interpretability, trust, and factual dependability in AI-generated material for sustainability underscore the need for expert validation and ongoing refinement [22, 59, 161].

4.5.2 Persuasion. Among the different findings, it seems there is a consensus on the effectiveness of social feedback over factual feedback across various domains. Studies such as [71, 72, 166] consistently show that PCAs providing social evaluative feedback – particularly negative social

feedback – tend to be more effective in altering behavior than those delivering neutral or factual information. This pattern holds in both robotic and virtual agents, where evaluative cues (e.g., facial expressions, tone of voice, verbal reactions) amplify the perceived relevance and urgency of the message, thereby increasing compliance with environmentally desirable behaviors.

Embodiment and anthropomorphism also emerge as critical factors that enhance persuasive potential. Multiple studies [24, 147, 166] suggest that the physical presence of a robot or human-like conversational features increase perceived social presence, trustworthiness, and credibility, which in turn bolster the PCA's persuasive impact. In particular, embodied agents were found to be more effective in exerting social influence, especially in contexts involving children or where emotional bonding was relevant [11, 105].

Personalization is widely recognized as a beneficial design strategy in PCA-mediated persuasion. [10, 19, 65] show that tailoring feedback and recommendations to the user's knowledge, preferences, and behavioral stage enhances both receptivity and perceived relevance, thereby supporting behavior change. Latest technologies based on LLMs even pushed the boundaries for personalized interaction, creating agents that could automatically adapt to users' preferences and behavior. However, as highlighted by Majid et al. [107], the perceived intrusiveness of personalization can sometimes undermine trust and credibility, indicating the need for careful contextualization and user-centered design.

The persuasive effect of PCAs is further supported by integration with motivational theories and behavior change models. Applications grounded in **Motivational Interviewing (MI)** and the **Trans-Theoretical Model (TTM)** [19, 174] demonstrate enhanced efficacy, particularly when agents express empathy, elicit "change talk", and support self-efficacy. This design approach was especially effective for male users when MI techniques were applied in dietary behavior change scenarios [174].

Conversational style and multimodality also contribute significantly to persuasion. For instance, [11, 75, 90] indicate that multimedia presence (e.g., voice, avatar presence) and emotionally resonant dialogues foster greater emotional attachment and responsiveness on the final users. Notably, emotionally positive strategies in conversational interaction were found to be more persuasive than purely rational messaging, especially among users with lower pre-existing environmental awareness, as argued by Berney et al. [11].

Still, strategic timing and contextual integration of PCA feedback, as highlighted in Bourgeois et al. [14], influence its effectiveness. Feedback that is timely, actionable, and situated at the point of decision-making yields greater behavioral adherence than delayed or retrospective feedback. Relatedly, studies underscore the importance of perceived autonomy and user control [5, 40], showing that less intrusive, user-initiated interactions are often preferred and more persuasive.

Interactive features and gamified elements, while enhancing engagement, do not always directly correlate with behavioral outcomes. Yamawaki et al. [171] found increased user vanity and perceived interaction with an agent, yet no significant behavioral changes in terms of donation or water use. Conversely, in studies such as [62, 105], the combination of gamification, feedback, and physical or visual interaction did support sustained engagement and attitude shifts, particularly in younger demographics.

Finally, even if it was not one of our primary points of focus for the survey, the role of trust, credibility, and source reliability is repeatedly emphasized. Users are more likely to be persuaded by PCAs perceived as trustworthy, accurate, and aligned with user values [10, 95, 107].

4.5.3 Conversation and Technology. The reviewed articles present an expansive set of insights on the design and development of Persuasive Conversational Agents, specifically emphasizing their dialogic design, system architectures, modality choices, and implementation contexts. A central

theme across these contributions underscores the importance of Natural Language Processing and Large Language Models as technological enablers of adaptive, personalized, and responsive communication. For instance, systems built upon GPT-based architectures demonstrate the potential for real-time, context-aware dialogue, whether in domestic energy management [170], sustainability education [175], or innovative tourism platforms [154].

Multimodal interaction emerges as a particularly salient feature, enhancing the persuasive efficacy of PCAs by integrating text, voice, and visual modalities. Social robots like iCat and Pepper, as shown in [10, 71, 72], exploit embodied communication, combining verbal cues with facial expressions and gestures. These multimodal capabilities contribute significantly to believability and user engagement, particularly in settings involving children or users with low technical literacy. Similarly, integrating graphical dashboards and avatars in systems (e.g., like Leafy proposed by Giudici et al. [62]) or Smart Mirror-based agents demonstrates how visual components can augment user understanding and behavioral motivation, echoing previous work in the literature [32, 136, 149].

Several implementations, such as those documented by [40, 61], highlight the tension between initiating conversations (proactivity) and responding to user input (reactivity), with implications for user acceptance and perceived intrusiveness. Timing of interventions, as emphasized by Majid et al. [107], plays a pivotal role in influencing behavioral outcomes, suggesting the need for fine-tuned conversation triggers aligned with user routines and contextual cues.

In terms of system architecture, modularity and integration with existing platforms are recurrently identified as key design principles. Studies such as [27, 63, 87, 131] present architectures combining NLP engines, IoT middleware, and cloud services to facilitate seamless, scalable interactions. RAG strategies are gaining traction, enabling PCAs to connect LLM outputs with real-time external data sources dynamically [17, 170], thereby improving response relevance and trustworthiness.

The embodiment and anthropomorphization of PCAs further modulate user perception. Human-like features – ranging from avatars and voice modulation to personal greetings – contribute to social presence and trust [45, 147]. However, other findings [71, 72] suggest that the effectiveness of social feedback might not necessarily depend on the robot's perceived agency but rather on the consistency and relevance of the feedback provided.

Finally, context-aware agents, informed by sensor data or an appropriate user modeling and behavioral analysis, deliver more persuasive and relevant feedback [75, 124, 161]. These systems tailor their outputs based on individual behavior, preferences, or environmental conditions, enhancing user engagement and behavioral alignment with environmental sustainability.

5 Discussion

The surveyed literature underscores several prominent research gaps at the intersection of persuasive technology, HCI conversational interaction, and sustainability, particularly in relation to the three main dimensions under analysis (i.e., sustainability topics addressed, persuasive effectiveness, and conversational interaction). These gaps will be critically discussed in this section, and they are functional to shape the research agenda and guidelines for future work in the field, both summarized in the following section (i.e., Section 6).

A recurrent gap in the articles lies in the evaluation of persuasion effectiveness and long-term behavioral and attitudinal changes in users' positive environmental behavior. Many studies develop prototypes or demonstrate short-term effects, but few examine long-term behavioral impact or conduct longitudinal evaluations to assess the sustained influence of persuasive technologies on pro-environmental attitudes [10, 24, 45, 60, 69, 131], taking also into consideration that some interventions focus on self-reported data, without direct measurement of actual behavior change in real-world settings [19, 174].

The persuasion strategies adopted in the current PCAs for environmental sustainability reveal both valuable insights and limitations. Feedback and monitoring approaches dominate, consistent with established principles in Persuasive Technology [55, 114], also for environmental sustainability [1]. In addition, while many systems implicitly address environmental sustainability, the range of SDGs engaged remains narrow. There is limited integration of SDG frameworks in system design or evaluation, mainly focused on Responsible Consumption and Production (SDG 12) and Affordable and Clean Energy (SDG 7), reflecting a focus on behaviors with relatively immediate, tangible outcomes for final users [35, 169]. For example, many examined articles addressed household energy conservation or encouraged more aware consumption, highlighting an effort on small-scale individual behaviors rather than linking them to a broader and global ecological impact (cf. [28]). While this emphasis affirms the potential for PCAs to prompt home eco-related choices, it also signals an underexplored dimension of additional Sustainable Development Goals, such as equitable resource allocation and enhanced community resilience [30, 53]. Still, few studies address interconnected goals comprehensively or synergistically [17, 82]. Moreover, equity-related goals are rarely engaged in environmental sustainability, for example, addressing issues of accessibility, inclusivity, and intersectionality [87, 121, 127]. Future investigations could expand the scope of PCAs to lower-addressed SDGs, integrating and combining different goals to establish a multidimensional sustainability framework of action.

A salient gap pertains to personalization and user modeling. Although personalization is often mentioned as a design goal, there is limited understanding of how individual differences – such as personality traits, demographics, cultural contexts, or prior environmental knowledge – influence the effectiveness of persuasive strategies on the environmental behaviour of the users [72, 90, 107], similar to previous findings from the literature [89]. In particular, the role of individual traits in modulating responses to feedback, nudges, or storytelling remains underexplored [52, 116]. Furthermore, while some studies emphasize tailoring persuasive strategies, actual implementations of adaptive and context-aware dialogue systems remain scarce [139, 170]. The conceptualization and operationalization of persuasion itself also reveal gaps. Many articles implement basic persuasive elements (e.g., reminders, tips), yet fail to rigorously test or compare different persuasive techniques (e.g., social norms, emotional appeals, authority-based messaging) or consider the psychological mechanisms underlying their effectiveness [45, 71, 101]. The limited investigation into multi-strategy and combined persuasion methods also constrains our understanding of how best to structure persuasive dialogues for sustainability [60].

Another aspect to consider is the technological landscape reported in the set of analyzed articles on PCA for environmental sustainability. Many implementations (around 48%) still rely on rule-based architectures (as shown in Figure 12) or lack advanced capabilities in natural language understanding, dialogue management, or multimodal interaction [27, 65, 131]. Such rule-based design implementation often ensures consistency in the messages delivered but can limit the sophistication of the user experience, whereas LLM-based agents could more dynamically adapt to user needs and contextual factors while also carrying risks of factual inaccuracy (i.e., hallucination) [79].

Although emerging studies experiment with LLMs, their use in environmental or sustainability domains remains nascent and raises concerns regarding bias, ethical, and sustainability deployment [59, 101, 126]. Additionally, integration with physical systems – such as robots, smart devices, or IoT infrastructures – often lacks scalability, robustness, or clear user value [5, 62, 147].

Moreover, the UX design of PCAs for environmental sustainability was addressed with different modalities and interaction flows, with half of the reviewed articles relying on text-based interfaces and the other set adopting voice-based channels, social robots, or multimodal platforms [51]. Speech-based systems could also enhance the anthropomorphic qualities of the agent, facilitating rapport, whereas text-based ones can offer reflective, asynchronous interaction (cf. [64]). Yet direct

Fig. 12. PCA's response generation methodology over years.

comparative studies of the two modalities remain unexplored; addressing such friction could help developers refine PCAs for real-world user populations whose preferences, technological access, persuasive effectiveness, and environmentally conscious actions vary significantly.

The proactivity of PCAs often proves decisive in capturing attention at critical moments [155]. Such “push-driven” approaches align with broader evidence on environmental-related behavior change interventions, suggesting that timely reminders can effectively nudge individuals toward more sustainable actions. However, an emphasis on agent-driven interactions can lead to perceived intrusiveness or diminished user autonomy [146], pointing toward finding a balance between beneficial prompting and respect for personal agency.

A significant research gap involves the limited diversity in application contexts and populations. First of all, the majority of existing studies are conducted in controlled environments with small, homogeneous participant groups (mainly university-student samples), restricting generalizability [10, 63, 75], posing challenges for external validity [21, 98]. Similarly, most of the published findings are based on “case studies” that often lead to incomparable (even contradictory) results, particularly those concerning effectiveness. For instance, Isaza-Giraldo et al. [81] advocated for positive feedback as a common persuasive technique with satisfactory outcomes, while – in the opposite way – [71, 72] reported on the effectiveness of negative feedback for effective persuasion. In addition, very few studies are deployed in ecologically valid (*in-the-wild*) [142, 143] studies or include underrepresented geographical and cultural contexts [95, 106] as well as evaluation for a prolonged period of time [12] – since the article under review rarely extending beyond a few weeks. This still raises concerns about the persistence of behavioral changes, as well as the potential for rebound effects [68] or “green fatigue” [153] caused by the PCA that pushes to more sustainable behavior.

At the political and societal levels, new sustainable interventions emphasize collective efforts [30, 162], whereas most of the reviewed studies focus on influencing individual actions. The design, development, and evaluation of networked multi-user PCAs that operate at community-level, e.g., in contexts of shared energy systems [133, 134] or communal waste initiatives [176], represent a promising but largely unexplored area of research. Expanding PCAs to encompass group negotiations and multi-user interactions could amplify impact, but it also demands more complex, context-specific user modeling and advanced multi-user dialogue management systems. In addition, it opens new challenges in integrating ethical and privacy guidelines, given the potential manipulation and disclosure of sensitive data when multiple users are involved in the dialogue.

Additionally, in terms of ethical considerations, a growing number of works highlight the need for normative frameworks to guide the development and deployment of environmental-based persuasive systems. Topics such as user autonomy, consent, data privacy, and the ethics of emotional manipulation are underexplored despite their crucial role in persuasive interventions on sensitive domains as environmental sustainability [10, 124, 154]. Finally, it must be considered that LLM-based PCA – throughout their lifecycle – have a significant impact on the environment and energy consumption [50, 85, 102], especially because of their high energy consumption during training and deployment [141]. Rule-based chatbots, on the other hand, are more environmentally friendly, requiring less energy and leaving a smaller carbon footprint [85]. According to McTear et al. [113], both strategies (LLMs and rule-based chatbots) have benefits and drawbacks that future work must consider and comparatively assess.

6 Guidelines

In this section, we present actionable recommendations distilled from our survey, which can support researchers and practitioners in the design, development, and assessment of PCAs for environmental sustainability. Lastly, we offer a checklist designed to guide the reporting of future evaluation studies in the field.

6.1 Recommendations

Starting from the in-depth analysis performed on the surveyed articles and their discussion, we produced – and reported in this section – a set of recommendations to guide both practitioners (e.g., interaction and conversation designers and technology developers) and researchers in the fields of Persuasive Conversational Agents for environmental sustainability.

(1) *Transparent and rigorous study designs.*

To assess different persuasive techniques in conversational agents for sustainability, future studies should include more randomized trials, control groups, or mixed-method designs that are able to create polls of different data (even from different sources). Reporting on sample demographics and data analysis procedures is also critical for reproducibility and guiding future research.

(2) *Longitudinal and real-world evaluations.*

To evaluate the impact and persistence of PCAs for environmental sustainability, future studies should use longer time frames and real-world scenarios that extend beyond the short-term laboratory environment. Incorporating actual, logged behavioral measures along with qualitative sustainability insights can help determine whether the persuasive impacts duration over time with a system deployed in the wild.

(3) *Embed cultural and contextual tailoring.*

Directly connected to the previous point, analyzed articles and existing systems assume a homogeneous user base, limiting their applicability. Future green PCAs could incorporate cultural norms, local environmental challenges, and region-specific behavior patterns to make sustainability messages more relatable and tailored to users' daily sustainability challenges.

(4) *Multi-strategy persuasion analysis.*

While single-strategy approaches (e.g., feedback strategy only) are still popular, integrating various persuasion strategies (e.g., social comparison, rewards, self-monitoring) can improve effectiveness in having more positive environmental behaviours. Researchers can create adaptable algorithms that swap between persuasive methods as consumers advance

through different levels of involvement or motivation. This method is supported by recognized behavior-change frameworks (e.g., the Transtheoretical Model [137]), which provide indicators for when a particular user may benefit the most from various persuasive techniques.

(5) *Design for multiple users and collective impact.*

Individual behaviors have been analyzed and are crucial; however, they only reflect one aspect of long-term development. This specific research domain should look at how PCAs can help with collective decision-making, such as in multi-person families or workplace teams in which they are usually placed. Such a branch of research also opens up the possibility of advancing dialogue management capabilities to handle concurrent prompts while addressing group dynamics (e.g., consensus-building, decision-making).

(6) *Generative AI explainability, ethical, and privacy concerns.*

To strike a balance between flexibility, trust, and transparency, PCAs for environmental sustainability powered by LLMs or advanced AI approaches should include **explainable AI (XAI)** [122]. Short, user-friendly explanations of why certain suggestions are made or how personal data opens research to understand if there is an increase in user understanding, trust, and acceptance. Such an aspect is particularly sensitive in sectors such as sustainability, where ethical, privacy, and social concerns might influence motivations. This technique can also help reduce the hazards associated with LLM hallucinations and provide people with access to the data or reasoning process under a specific PCA suggestion or prompt.

(7) *Investigate the environmental footprint of LLM-based PCAs.*

As LLMs become increasingly prevalent, future research should explicitly critically reflect [15] and evaluate [63] both the direct and indirect energy costs associated with training, deploying and integrating these models in new PCAs. Emphasis should be placed on ensuring that the design of emerging LLM-based persuasive conversational systems in the field remains aligned with broader sustainability objectives.

6.2 Reporting Checklist

This section describes a *reporting checklist* (Table 2) for describing future works on Persuasive Conversational Agents for environmental sustainability. Such a checklist aims at guiding future work in this domain by reporting all the information on the design, the main feature, and their empirical evaluation of such Conversational Agents. The reporting checklist is based on the findings and the difficulties encountered in reporting variables for the current review, as well as reconnecting with the conceptual framework described in Section 2.2. Even if it is not exhaustive, it is a good starting point for researchers when they want to report studies on green Persuasive Conversational Agents effectively.

- (1) From the *conversational agent design* perspective, we recommend future researchers specify the requirements and design choices adopted to build such Persuasive Conversational Agents. Among the possible features of PCA are input and output modalities, embodiment and shape, gender, conversational design, additional capabilities (e.g., emotion recognition), and integration with the external environment. In the previous work of Giudici et al. [61], researchers could find a framework to support the definition of the main feature of a Conversational Agent for sustainability.
- (2) From a *persuasion* point of view, we recommend that future researchers pinpoint the agent's persuasion strategies (possibly referring to Michie et al. [114]), This specification allows

Table 2. Checklist to Systematically Report Empirical Studies on Persuasive Conversational Agents for Environmental Sustainability

Category	List of Items	Example
<i>Conversational Agent Design</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Input Interaction Modalities <input type="checkbox"/> Output Interaction Modalities <input type="checkbox"/> Embodiment and Shape of the Agent <input type="checkbox"/> Gender of the Agent <input type="checkbox"/> Conversation Design <input type="checkbox"/> Additional Capabilities <input type="checkbox"/> Integration with the External Environment	speech-based, text-based, etc. speech-based, text-based, etc. physical robot, virtual agent, chatbot, etc. female, male, neutral, etc. rule-based, knowledge-based, etc. emotion recognition, etc. smart plugs connection, transportation API, etc.
<i>Persuasion</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Persuasion Strategy(ies) <input type="checkbox"/> Persuasion Theory (if any)	Feedback and Monitoring, Goal Setting, etc.
<i>Sustainable Topic</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> SDG <input type="checkbox"/> Detailed Description	Affordable and Clean Energy (7), etc. e.g., <i>decreasing overall home electric consumption</i>
<i>Demographics</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Sample Size <input type="checkbox"/> Age <input type="checkbox"/> Educational Level <input type="checkbox"/> Gender Distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Prior Experience with agents	reporting number of people involved in the study reporting mean and SD primary school, university, etc. equal, percentage, etc. zero, little, expert, etc.
<i>Empirical Study</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Setting <input type="checkbox"/> Study design <input type="checkbox"/> Study duration <input type="checkbox"/> Nature of the Prototype <input type="checkbox"/> Collected Data Type <input type="checkbox"/> Data Collection Method	lab setting, home, etc. within-subject, between-subject, etc. hours, days, months, etc. Wizard of Oz, coded, etc. objective, subjective, etc. questionnaires, interview, etc.

readers a better understanding of the theoretical feature underlying the agent and improves the replicability of the scientific work. In addition, they also have to consider if the approach adopted is grounded and associated with a specific Persuasion Theory.

- (3) Addressing the *sustainable topic*, researchers should identify their conversational agents' corresponding SDGs and provide a detailed description of how they contribute to reaching the specific goal(s).

For example, in the case of a persuasive conversational agent that helps users optimize and avoid the food waste in their fridge, it must be classified into the *Responsible Consumption and Production* (SDG 12). In addition, researchers should specify that the agent contributes to the goal by using food waste reduction in the household context.

- (4) Reporting the data about participants in empirical evaluation, researchers have to brief the *demographics* of the poll. It must include sample size, age of participants, educational level, gender distribution, and prior experience with conversational agents.
- (5) Finally, *empirical studies* must report key information for the scientific community evaluation. In the case of Persuasive Conversational Agents for sustainability, it is crucial to state the study's setting. In addition, researchers should report the study design, its duration, and the type and method of data collection. Finally, it is also relevant to report information on the nature of the prototype, useful to deeply understand the *conversational agent design* (in the first point).

7 Limitations

The value of our survey lies in its review of the current landscape of an emerging topic and its provision of a road map for future research and practice. However, we acknowledge that the study

may have some limitations. Some relevant articles may have been unintentionally excluded from our review despite our efforts to follow a systematic and standardized method of selection and analysis. We exhaustively identified articles that met the inclusion/exclusion criteria, employed backward and forward chaining of citations for included articles to track additional relevant studies, and involved multiple researchers in the search process, concluding with a final discussion on the relevance and completeness of the results.

One of the difficulties was evaluating the scientific quality of some selected articles, partly due to the scarcity of information on various aspects and the different (sometimes limited) reporting methods. Incomplete information may have left some relevant features unrevealed or obscure, resulting in their exclusion from our analysis. For instance, several works used persuasive techniques without explicitly grounding these strategies in persuasive theories. The reporting checklist discussed in Section 6.2 provides a framework for better reporting future work in the field and can help mitigate these issues in future research. Finally, the reported evaluation studies were very heterogeneous regarding empirical research methods, settings, participants, tasks, and durations, making it difficult to derive insights that can be generalized to other evaluation contexts.

Finally, given the nascent nature of this research stream, there is a scarcity of works focused on sustainability, specific SDGs, and associated or mix of such themes. Consequently, the results about the “topic” variable are limited and do not provide significant insights. As the field evolves and the range of sustainability topics addressed by future Persuasive Conversational Agents expands, it will become possible to perform more focused analyses of this specific design dimension.

8 Conclusion

We presented a survey on Persuasive Conversational Agents for environmental sustainability as an innovative interaction paradigm to move toward a green world and more aware of energy consumption.

The 52 articles reviewed provide a comprehensive overview of the main results achieved in the last decade of scientific work in the field. They highlight that various conversational technologies have been explored and a wide range of UX design features have been adopted. However, the articles also indicate some common trends:

- the use of *Feedback and Monitoring* as the primary persuasion strategy, with a focus on *Responsible Consumption and Production (SDG 12)* as the Sustainable Development Goal addressed.
- the integration of conversational solutions for persuasive sustainability with external “smart” environments (i.e., ubiquitous computing).
- the evaluation of conversational solutions through short-term studies typically involves interaction with the tool and questionnaires.

The survey discusses the key takeaways from the reviewed works and offers several suggestions (referred as recommendations) for further research and development in the area of Persuasive Conversational Agents for environmental sustainability. Some of these suggestions could also inspire practitioners and researchers in other application domains for conversational agents. In addition, for future studies on Persuasive Conversational Agents for environmental sustainability, we offer a reporting checklist. The goal of the checklist is to serve as a guide for researchers reporting the factors we believe are essential to fully describe such agents.

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Appendix

A List of Surveyed Articles

This appendix lists the 52 articles included in this survey and cited in Table 3. In addition, the supplementary material of this manuscript provides an Excel file that reports all the analyses carried out on the surveyed articles.

Table 3. Table Reporting the Articles Included in this Survey on Persuasive Conversational Agents for Environmental Sustainability

#	Title	Author(s)	Year	Reference
1	A robot that says “bad!”: Using negative and positive social feedback from a robotic agent to save energy	Jaap Ham, Cees Midden	2009	[71]
2	Social influence of a persuasive agent: The role of agent embodiment and evaluative feedback	Vossen S., Ham J., Midden C.	2009	[166]
3	The illusion of agency: The influence of the agency of an artificial agent on its persuasive power	Midden C., Ham J.	2012	[115]
4	Designing motivation using persuasive ambient mirrors	Tatsuo Nakajima, Vili Lehdonvirta	2013	[124]
5	A Persuasive Robot to Stimulate Energy Conservation: The Influence of Positive and Negative Social Feedback and Task Similarity on Energy-Consumption Behavior	Ham J., Midden C.J.H.	2014	[72]
6	Live capture of energy-related knowledge into BIM systems	Motawa I., Janarthanam S., Almarshad A.	2014	[120]
7	Conversations with my washing machine: an in-the-wild study of demand shifting with self-generated energy	Jacky Bourgeois, Janet van der Linden, Gerd Kortuem, Blaine A. Price, and Christopher Rimmer	2014	[14]
8	Conforming to an artificial majority: persuasive effects of a group of artificial agents	C Midden, J Ham, J Baten	2015	[116]
9	Tariff Agent: Interacting with a Future Smart Energy System at Home	Alper T. Alan, Enrico Costanza, Sarvapali D. Ramchurn, Joel Fischer, Tom Rodden, and Nicholas R. Jennings	2016	[5]
10	Buildings with persona: Towards effective building-occupant communication	Khashe S., Lucas G., Becerik-Gerber B., Gratch J.	2017	[90]
11	Convincing Conversations: Using a Computer-Based Dialogue System to Promote a Plant-Based Diet	Zaal E.L.; Mills G.J.; Hagen A.; Huisman C.A.; Hoeks J.C.J.	2017	[174]
12	Designing conversational agents for energy feedback	Gnewuch U., Morana S., Heckmann C., Maedche A.	2018	[65]
13	Intrusive Plug Management System Using Chatbots in Office Environments	Ramasubbu, D; KrishnamoorthyBaskaran; Yann, G	2018	[139]
14	Virtual assistant for IoT process management, using a middleware	Chilcañán D., Navas P., Escobar M.	2018	[27]
15	Promoting sustainable mobility beliefs with persuasive and anthropomorphic design: Insights from an experiment with a conversational agent	Diederich S., Lichtenberg S., Brendel A.B., Trang S.	2019	[45]
16	Zero Food Waste: Food wastage sustaining mobile application	M. D. C. J. Gunawardane; H. A. N. Pushpakumara; E. N. M. R. L. Navarathne; S. Lokuliyana; K. T. I. Kelaniyage; N. Gamage	2019	[69]

(Continued)

Table 3. Continued

#	Title	Author(s)	Year	Reference
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18	Factors influencing adoption intention of ai powered chatbot for public transport services within a smart city	Kuberkar S., Singhal T.K.	2020	[95]
19	Greening food consumption using chatbots as behavioral change agent	Cacanindin N.M., Palaoag T.D.	2020	[19]
20	GreenLife: A Persuasive Social Robot to Enhance the Sustainable Behavior in shared Living Spaces	Beheshtian N., Moradi S., Ahtinen A., Väänänen K., Kähkönen K., Laine M.	2020	[10]
21	Let's Learn Biodiversity with a Virtual Robot?	Ferreira, MJ; Oliveira, R; Olim, SC; Nisi, V; Paiva, A	2020	[52]
22	"Meet, greet and learn: introducing Bern!" Saving energy through voice interaction with your smart thermostat	S de Vos, B Rolvink, N Güneş, S San Nguyen...	2020	[40]
23	An experimental study on promotion of pro-environmental behavior focusing on "vanity" for interactive agent	M Yamawaki, K Ueda, Y Sakamoto, H Ishii...	2020	[171]
24	EnviRobots: How Human-Robot Interaction Can Facilitate Sustainable Behavior	Scheutz, C; Law, T; Scheutz, M	2021	[147]
25	PepeRecycle: Improving Children's Attitude Toward Recycling by Playing with a Social Robot	Castellano, G; De Carolis, B; D'Errico, F; Macchiarulo, N; Rossano, V	2021	[24]
26	Talking to plants: An IoT system supporting human-plant interactions and learning	Tabuenca B., Greller W., Hernández-Leo D., Gilarranz-Casado C., García-Alcántara V., Tovar E.	2021	[157]
27	Chatbot as a Persuasive Technology to Promote Responsible Recycling in the City of Lima	Flores K.A.F.; Perez J.J.G.; Sanchez L.M.C.	2022	[54]
28	Arabic Mini-ClimateGPT: A Climate Change and Sustainability Tailored Arabic LLM	Mullappilly S.S.; Shaker A.; Thawkar O.; Cholakkal H.; Anwer R.M.; Khan S.; Khan F.S.	2023	[121]
29	Leafy: Enhancing Home Energy Efficiency through Gamified Experience with a Conversational Smart Mirror	Giudici M.; Crovari P.; Garzotto F.	2023	[62]
30	Assessing LLMs Responses in the Field of Domestic Sustainability: An Exploratory Study	Giudici M.; Abbo G.A.; Belotti O.; Braccini A.; Dubini F.; Izzo R.A.; Crovari P.; Garzotto F.	2023	[59]
31	CANDY: A framework to design Conversational AgeNts for Domestic sustainability	Giudici M.; Crovari P.; Garzotto F.	2023	[61]
32	Integrating Generative AI and IoT for Sustainable Smart Tourism Destinations	Suanpang P.; Pothipassa P.	2024	[154]
33	Eternagram: Probing Player Atitudes in Alternate Climate Scenarios Through a ChatGPT-Driven Text Adventure	Zhou S.; Hendra L.B.; Zhang Q.; Holopainen J.; Lc R.	2024	[175]
34	A novel approach to sustainable behavior enhancement through AI-driven carbon footprint assessment and real-time analytics	Jasmy A.J.; Ismail H.; Aljneibi N.	2024	[82]
35	Healthy and Sustainable Meals Recommendation Exploiting Food Retrieval and Large Language Models	Petruzzelli A.; Musto C.; Di Carlo M.C.; Tempesta G.; Semeraro G.	2024	[135]

(Continued)

Table 3. Continued

#	Title	Author(s)	Year	Reference
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37	Study of Promoting Energy Saving Behavior in Homes with Personalized Adaptive Interaction	Hirai S.; Okamoto H.; Nakata T.; Chen S.; Saiki S.; Nakamura M.	2024	[75]
38	AI Insights: Unveiling UK Energy Consumption with Langchain Powered Chatbots	Justice K.; Vakaj E.; Dridi A.	2024	[87]
39	Promoting pro-environmental behaviour spillover through chatbots	Majid G.M.; Tussyadiah I.; Kim Y.R.; Chen J.L.	2024	[107]
40	Evaluating Non-Expert Stakeholder Interaction with Artificial Intelligence on Energy Urban Domain Using VIRTISI: The Case of ChatGPT	Tsihrintzis G.A.; Sarmas E.; Marinakis V.; Panagoulas D.; Tsihrintzi E.-A.; Virvou M.	2024	[161]
41	Assessing Italian Large Language Models on Energy Feedback Generation: A Human Evaluation Study	Sanguinetti M.; Pani A.; Perniciano A.; Zedda L.; Loddo A.; Atzori M.	2024	[145]
42	Care-Based Eco-Feedback Augmented with Generative AI: Fostering Pro-Environmental Behavior through Emotional Attachment	Berney M.; Ouazaki A.; Macko V.; Kocher B.; Holzer A.	2024	[11]
43	Prompt-Gaming: A Pilot Study on LLM-Evaluating Agent in a Meaningful Energy Game	Isaza-Giraldo A.; Bala P.; Campos P.F.; Pereira L.	2024	[81]
44	Misrepresentation or inclusion: promises of generative artificial intelligence in climate change education	Nguyen H.; Nguyen V.; Ludovise S.; Santagata R.	2024	[126]
45	Responsible Configuration Using LLM-based Sustainability-Aware Explanations	Lubos S.; Felfernig A.; Hotz L.; Tran T.N.T.; Polat-Erdeniz S.; Le V.-M.; Garber D.; El-Mansi M.	2024	[101]
46	Learning Waste Management from Interactive Quizzes and Adaptive GPT-guided Feedback	Sun Q.; Chien S.-Y.; Hsiao I.-H.	2024	[156]
47	Delivering Green Persuasion Strategies with a Conversational Agent: a Pilot Study	Giudici M.; Abbo G.A.; Crovari P.; Garzotto F.	2024	[60]
48	RoboRecycle Buddy: Enhancing Early Childhood Green Education and Recycling Habits Through Playful Interaction with a Social Robot	Mahmud S.; Kamel Z.; Singh A.; Kim J.-H.	2024	[105]
49	Exploring the Potential of Chatbots in Extending Tourists' Sustainable Travel Practices	Majid G.M.; Tussyadiah I.; Kim Y.R.	2024	[106]
50	Designing Home Automation Routines Using an LLM-Based Chatbot	Giudici M.; Padalino L.; Paolino G.; Paratici I.; Pascu A.I.; Garzotto F.	2024	[63]
51	Value-sensitive design of chatbots in environmental education: Supporting identity, connectedness, well-being and sustainability	Nguyen H.; Nguyen V.; Ludovise S.; Santagata R.	2025	[127]
52	A large language model-based platform for real-time building monitoring and occupant interaction	Xu Y.; Zhu S.; Cai J.; Chen J.; Li S.	2025	[170]

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